

Reliable Machine Learning Acceleration for Future Space Processors and FPGAs: LEON, NOEL-V and TASTE

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Introduction and Motivation

- ⌘ Increasing interest in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in space missions: e.g. Mars Perseverance, Φ -Sat-1, OPS-SAT...
- ⌘ Existing space processors cannot keep up with their computational needs
- ⌘ Use of COTS devices in institutional missions is challenging:
 - ⌘ no radiation hardening \rightarrow cannot be (safely) used beyond LEO
 - ⌘ Non-space qualified software stacks, lack of RTOS support
- ⌘ We present two open source hardware designs to increase AI processing capabilities in space:
 - ⌘ Low-cost short vector unit to increase AI performance in space CPUs
 - ⌘ Low-cost Binarized Neural Network (BNN) accelerator based on TASTE

Low-Cost Short Vector Support for Space Processors

- ⌘ Hardware module designed for Gaisler's LEON3 and NOEL-V processors
- ⌘ Low-cost hardware unit to speed-up AI applications
 - ⌘ Special instructions selected by analyzing the most common ML operations
 - ⌘ 8-bit integer instructions are enough for ML [1]
- ⌘ SIMD architecture such as ARM's NEON
 - ⌘ But reduced hardware overhead by reusing the integer register file
 - ⌘ SWAR (SIMD within a register) concept inspired by [2] but combining ideas from mobile GPUs [3] too
- ⌘ Saturation option included for all instructions

[1] T. P. Jouppi et al. In-Datacenter Performance Analysis of a Tensor Processing Unit. ISCA, 2017

[2] Martin Danek. ESA IP Core Extensions for LEON2: daiFPU and SWAR. ESA TEC-ED & TEC-SW Final Presentation Days, May 2020.

[3] Trompouki, Towards General Purpose Computations on Low-end Mobile GPUs. DATE 2016. ³

SIMD: Architecture design

- Reusing the integer register file simplifies loading and managing the data in the registers
- Frequently found instructions in ML algorithms added: arithmetic, bitwise, min, max etc.
- Two pipeline stages:
 - Vector-Vector operations
 - Reduction operations
 - Bypasses when one is not used

SIMD: Architecture design

- ❧ Instructions encode the source and destination register and the operation code for each stage
 - ❧ Exploited unused opcodes in LEON3
 - ❧ Custom extensions for NOEL-V
- ❧ Additional embedded GPU inspired features are included:
 - ❧ Immediate instructions encode commonly used values (e.g. powers of 2)
 - ❧ Masking and Swizzling
 - ❧ Both configured using the special register %scr (SIMD control register)

SIMD: Programming

- ⌘ Assembler support has been included for the new SIMD instructions
- ⌘ The tests have been written in C using inline assembly
 - ⌘ Currently working on compiler support

```
1 unsigned char weights[32*32];
2 unsigned char next_layer[32*32];
3
4 /* Allocate short vectors to specific registers */
5 register unsigned int a asm("%g4");
6 register unsigned int b asm("%g5");
7 register unsigned int result asm("%g6");
8
9 /* initialise all a components to 0, ie a.xyzw=0 */
10 a = 0;
11 /* b.xyzw = weights[0].xyzw */
12 b = *((unsigned int*) &weights[0]);
13 /* result.xyzw = a.xyzw + b.xyzw */
14 asm("add_ %g4, %g5, %g6");
15 /* next_layer[0].xyzw = result.xyzw */
16 *((unsigned int*) &next_layer[0])=result;
```

Preliminary Evaluation: Hardware Overhead

We have implemented our design using Xilinx Vivado targeting Artix 7

⌘ Baseline LEON3-MIN@100MHz

Resource	SIMD Cost Absolute Value	% of increase w.r.t. baseline LEON3-MIN
LUTs	1869	25%
FF	168	5.9%

- ⌘ Only a fraction of the hardware cost of conventional vector implementations for embedded processors (25% vs 2X) [1]
- ⌘ The integration of the SIMD reduced the core frequency to 72MHz
 - ⌘ Currently working on design optimisation to achieve the original frequency

Preliminary Evaluation: ML Performance

⌘ Matrix multiplication speed-up compared to LEON3-MIN@100MHz

⌘ Essential building block in NN for fully connected and convolution layers

	Matrix size			
Data type	4x4	8x8	16x16	32x32
Int	2.45x	3.81x	3.08x	3.39x
Char	2.24x	3.59x	2.96x	3.31x

⌘ Complex inference application Cifar-10 from [1][2] speed-up:

Cifar-10	4.13x
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⌘ Performance improvements despite frequency reduction

[1] GPU4S Bench: Design and Implementation of an Open GPU Benchmarking Suite for Space On-board Processing. https://www.ac.upc.edu/app/research-reports/public/html/research_center_index-CAP-2019,en.html

[2] GPU4S (GPUs for Space): Are we there yet? & OBPMark (On-Board Processing Benchmarks) – Open Source Computational Performance Benchmarks for Space Applications, OBDP 2021

FPGA Binary Neural Network (BNN) Accelerator

Combination of CPU, TASTE framework and a BNN FPGA Accelerator

1. CPU loads feature vector

2. ESA's Model-Based TASTE framework handles the communication to accelerator

3. Custom-designed BNN Accelerator on the FPGA performs inference step

4. CPU receives prediction result

Project Properties

⌘ Operation principle

- ⌘ Inference off-loading to the FPGA BNN accelerator

⌘ Reconfigurable design through the FPGA

- ⌘ Flexible adaption to neural network parameters
- ⌘ Scalable parallelism

⌘ Reliable and Open Source from the ground up:

- ⌘ TASTE correct-by-construction communication: software driver and hardware communication mechanism generation
- ⌘ Hand-written VHDL open source code for the accelerator

Binarized Neural Networks

Binarization

- MAC operation is simplified to XNOR and set bit count operation
- Reduces memory usage up to 1/32
- Only marginal performance loss shown in scientific literature

FPGA Binary Neural Network Accelerator

Basic principle: Fully connected layer cells attached through buffers

Convolutional layer possible through parallel fully connected layers and reconnecting of the feature maps

Why is this very fast?

⌘ Parallelization inside layer

- ⌘ Parallel bitwise execution only limited by loading weights from BRAM

⌘ Pipelining over layers

- ⌘ Instead of sequential calculation on the CPU, the first layer can start with the next feature vector after completing the previous one

⌘ Low memory usage

- ⌘ Effective load and store of weights

Preliminary Evaluation on Simulation

Clock cycles needed for one MNIST pass through fully connected layer with size (512, 512) on a LEON3 and on the accelerator

Speed Up of about 74x. But:

- ⌘ FPGA operates at different frequency
 - ⌘ Communication overhead is not considered
 - ⌘ LEON3 simulation only with TSIM
- Speed up expected to be smaller in reality

⌘ From simulation to hardware

- ⌘ LEON3 and BNN accelerator not connected yet
- ⌘ Simulation and verification was only performed separately

⌘ Python Code generator integrated with the TASTE framework

- ⌘ Integrating binarized layer training into a big DL library like PyTorch
- ⌘ After training, get parameters and layer configurations
- ⌘ Optimize parallelization scheme and generate VHDL code for the accelerator in a complete model-based manner

Conclusions and Future Work

- ⌘ **Two work-in-progress open source hardware designs for reliable machine learning acceleration of space on-board systems:**
 - ⌘ A low-cost AI vector unit for LEON3 and NOEL-V, achieving speedups in matrix multiplication of up to 3.8x and 4.13x in a complex inference chain
 - ⌘ Improve CPU frequency to match baseline design
 - ⌘ Full compiler support
 - ⌘ An FPGA BNN neural network accelerator achieving theoretical speedups of 74x compared to a baseline LEON3 processor
 - ⌘ Move from simulation to FPGA
 - ⌘ Automatic code generation integrated with TASTE and PyTorch
 - ⌘ Both provide promising preliminary results
 - ⌘ Evaluation with space-relevant ML benchmarks: OBPMark and MLAB presented at OBDP 2021

References and Acknowledgements

- ⌘ Both projects participate in the Xilinx Open Hardware Design Competition 2021 (Europe):
 - ⌘ Vector Unit: <https://gitlab.bsc.es/msolebon/grlib-ai-extension>
 - ⌘ BNN Accelerator: www.github.com/JannisWolf/fpga_bnn_accelerator
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